

1. Allgemeine Angaben

Antrag auf Gewährung von Schiffzeit für das FS POSEIDON.

1.1 Nutzer¹

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1.2 Thema

Tracking an **Upwelling Patch**: unravel biogeochemical cycles and air-sea **EX**change of climate **AC**tive Trace gases

Research area: North east Atlantic; upwelling area off the coast of Mauritania

1.3 Kennwort

TUP:EXACT

1.4 Fachgebiet und Arbeitsrichtung

Chemical oceanography, physical oceanography, biological oceanography, biogeochemistry, air-sea interaction; implications for atmospheric processes.

1.5 Fahrtzeitraum und Großgeräte

Here I apply for shiptime on the R/V POSEIDON for a cruise in early 2018. The working area is the upwelling area off the Mauritanian coast between 17°N and 20°N. Spring time (February to April) is favorable since this is the time of the strongest upwelling. The proposed cruise is 21 days long (6 days of transit and 15 working days). The first station will be at 20°N, 17.3°W. The last station will be around 18°N, 17°W. Preferred start and end of the the cruise is Las Palmas/Spain, but Mindelo/Cape Verde would be a good alternative. No excessively large equipment will be needed.

1.6 Deutsche und englische Zusammenfassung

Zusammenfassung

In sog. „Eastern Boundary Upwelling Systems (EBUS)“ wird Tiefenwasser an die Oberfläche gebracht, das hohe Konzentrationen an Spurengasen (wie z.B. CO₂ und N₂O) und niedrige Konzentrationen an O₂ hat. Auf Grund der geographischen Lage von EBUS (Tropen/Subtropen), setzt dann eine starke biologische Produktion ein. Die aufgetriebenen Wassermassen treiben von der Küste in den offenen Ozean und geben große Mengen an CO₂ und N₂O an die Atmosphäre ab und nehmen O₂ auf. Gleichzeitig wird aber auch CO₂ durch biologische Prozesse aufgenommen und O₂ abgegeben. Die hohe Produktivität führt zur Ausbildung von Oberflächenfilmen (SML), die den Gasaustausch unterdrücken können. Die Auswirkungen sollen in einem Experiment untersucht werden: In einem frisch aufgetriebenen Wasserpaket soll ein Oberflächendrifter ausgesetzt werden, so dass wir diesem Wasserpaket folgen und ein extensives Messprogramm durchführen können: Messung von Spurengasen im Wasser und der Atmosphäre, Direktflussmessungen von CO₂, regelmäßige Beprobung des SML und Messungen der physikalischen Bedingungen. Diese Messungen werden uns helfen die

¹ Die Bezeichnung „Nutzer“ schließt sowohl weibliche als auch männliche Nutzer ein.

biologischen, chemischen und physikalischen Prozesse zu entflechten und das Verständnis von Auftriebsgebieten und deren globale Auswirkung verbessern.

Abstract

Eastern Boundary upwelling systems (EBUS) are well known to be highly productive regions. Water from deeper layers is brought to the surface and transports high loads of nutrients and trace gases (e.g. CO₂, N₂O) and water that is low in oxygen. Due to their geographical location in the tropics/subtropics enough light is available to start strong biological productivity. While water masses move away from the coast to the open ocean trace gases as CO₂ and N₂O are released to the atmosphere while oxygen is taken up. At the same time CO₂ is consumed by biological production and oxygen is produced. Due to this high productivity surfactants are building up at the sea surface. This surface micro layer (SML) is known to dampen air-sea gas exchange. Here we propose to deploy a drifter in a fresh upwelled water parcel in order to follow the water parcel for a time period of 15 days. During this time an extensive measuring program will be conducted consisting of continuous measurements of trace gases in the upwelling patch and the overlying atmosphere, direct flux measurements of CO₂, regular determination of the SML and measurements of the physical conditions of the water parcel. This sampling strategy will enable us to unravel the different biological, chemical and physical processes in the upwelling parcel and foster our knowledge about the impact of EBUS on global scales.

2. Stand der Forschung, eigene Vorarbeiten

2.1 Stand der Forschung und eigene Vorarbeiten

Importance of Eastern boundary upwelling systems

Eastern Boundary Upwelling systems (EBUS) are amongst the most productive regions of the world ocean, with importance both for fisheries and for the cycling of carbon in the ocean (Pauly & Christensen 1995). EBUS are linked to the subtropical gyres and thus are found in the tropics and subtropics. The upwelling along the west coasts of continents is driven by trade winds

Figure 1: Measurements of pCO₂, N₂O and oxygen in the surface water measured over a section off the Mauritanian coast. The section started in the open ocean (left) heading to the coast (Steinhoff et al. 2012).

acting in concert with the Coriolis force and injects nutrients from below the surface into the ocean's euphotic zone triggering high primary production (PP). Approximately 11% of global PP is generated in EBUS although they account for only about 1% of the ocean's surface area (Chavez & Toggweiler 1995).

The Canary Current Ecosystem is one of the four major EBUS and exhibits the strongest spatial and seasonal variability of PP, with more or less constant upwelling in its northern section (19°N – 33°N) and pronounced seasonality south of 19°N (Carr & Kearns 2003). The region off the Mauritanian coast between 17°N and 21°N is known as the transition zone between the constant and seasonal upwelling regimes (Wooster et al. 1976). This region experiences its peak

upwelling season in spring because of the most northern position of the intertropical convergence zone (ITCZ). Upwelling events can be identified by strong temperature drops (more than 6°C compared to the open ocean waters) and are found in a narrow band of 10-20km along the coast (Mittelstaedt 1983). This bands show the characteristically enhanced biological productivity, typical for EBUS.

Trace gases in EBUS

In addition to their high nutrient load, upwelled water masses are characterized by high concentration of gases, such as N₂O and CO₂, and low oxygen concentrations. Both, N₂O and CO₂ are strong greenhouse gases (e.g. Forster et al., 2007) and steadily increase in the atmosphere. While upwelling systems can be a source (mineralized carbon in the upwelled water masses) or a sink (PP) for CO₂, they have the potential to be hotspots for N₂O emissions (Arévalo-Martínez et al. 2015). Figure 1 shows pCO₂, N₂O and oxygen data recorded during a Poseidon cruise (P320-1, (Steinhoff et al. 2012)) in the Mauritanian upwelling, illustrating high supersaturation (with respect to the atmosphere) of CO₂ and N₂O and undersaturation of oxygen near the coast. As the upwelled water moves away from the coast the values of CO₂ and N₂O reach equilibrium with the atmosphere but oxygen becomes slightly supersaturated. Obviously there are concurrent and counteracting processes resulting in the observed patterns of dissolved gases. For example, when the water parcel is transported away from the coast, it will lose N₂O and CO₂ and take up oxygen due to air-sea exchange (ASE). At the same time biological activity consumes CO₂ and produces oxygen. The influence of sunlight is apparent in the diurnal patterns of the trace gases (Figure 2), which can be misinterpreted when not measured with high temporal resolution.

Due to the confounding effects of the different processes, it is still unclear if this area is a net source of CO₂ to the atmosphere (high supersaturation at the coast) or a net sink (high productivity). In order to estimate the net flux of CO₂ it is crucial to quantify the effect of the individual processes, such as biological production, mixing and air-sea gas exchange. Measuring gases in the surface water that are not influenced by PP (like N₂O (Kock et al. 2012)) or are produced/consumed by different pathways as CO₂ will enable us to unravel the different processes.

Figure 2: Diel cycle of oxygen, dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) and sea surface temperature. Data were recorded during the Meteor cruise M68-3 near the Mauritanian coast in an upwelled water parcel. Oxygen was measured using an Aanderaa oxygen optode. The green line is a calculated dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) anomaly (calculated from measured pCO₂ and estimated alkalinity); the green dots are measured DIC values. (Steinhoff, 2012, unpublished data)

Air-sea gas exchange

The mechanisms driving ASE have been studied using both lab experiments (e.g. Jähne & Haußecker, 1998) and field measurements (e.g. Ho et al., 2006). The most common way to calculate the flux, F , of any gas, G , across the air-sea interface is the so called bulk method:

$$F = k \cdot [c_{ocean}(G) - c_{atm}(G)],$$

where k is the gas transfer coefficient and $c_{ocean}(G)$ and $c_{atm}(G)$ are the gas concentrations in the ocean's surface and the overlying atmosphere, respectively. k is typically parameterized by horizontal wind speed, as wind speed is thought to be the main factor driving turbulence at the air-sea interface. Several empirical relationships have been established which relate k to wind speed, but these simple k - wind speed relationships are associated with a high degree of uncertainty. The resulting F strongly depends on which relationship is applied (Wanninkhof et al. 2009). Moreover, there is growing evidence that organic surface films resulting from high productivity might alter ASE. This is in line with laboratory studies that found that organic films dampen turbulent motions at the air-sea interface (Jähne et al. 1987). This implies that k in the traditional flux equation depends on other factors besides wind speed alone (Schmidt & Schneider 2011; Kock et al. 2012; Steinhoff et al. 2012; Tsai & Liu 2003). Tsai and Liu (2003) estimated that the net CO₂ uptake of the global oceans is reduced by 20 - 50% under the assumption of surface film coverage in high productivity regions. In a more recent study, Wurl et al. (2016) estimate that the CO₂ flux can be reduced up to 15% caused by the presence surface films. In the Mauritanian upwelling region Kock et al. (2012) could only close their mixed layer budget of N₂O when using a k parameterization that accounts for surfactants. Steinhoff et al. (2012) concluded for the same study area that commonly used parameterizations of k significantly overestimate ASE.

A different method of quantifying gas fluxes between the ocean and the atmosphere, which does not rely on parameterizations of k , is the eddy-covariance (EC) method (Businger 1986). The EC technique measures turbulent fluctuations directly, over an integrated surface area (flux footprint) without disturbing the surroundings. EC fluxes are determined by computing the covariance between simultaneously measured vertical wind fluctuations and fluctuations in the gas concentration of interest:

$$F = \langle w' C' \rangle$$

where primes denote fluctuations from the mean and the brackets denote time averaging. By measuring the EC F and ΔC simultaneously, one can directly determine the k value, which might be different for different surface conditions.

PP in upwelling areas has been estimated variously from modeling studies (Lachkar & Gruber 2012; Lachkar & Gruber 2011), using remotely sensed data as proxies (Behrenfeld et al. 2005; Messié et al. 2009), and from incubation measurements (Dugdale & Goering 1967). Minas et al. (1986) derived production estimates for the Mauritanian upwelling by direct measurements of nutrients and their subsequent decrease in combination with the heat flux of the surface water. However, there is evidence that nutrient uptake is not an ideal measure for productivity as the elemental ratio (C/N) can vary significantly during production (Sambrotto et al. 1993; Thomas et al. 1999) due to changing communities and available nutrients (Körtzinger et al. 2001; Koeve 2004). Loucaides et al. (2012) estimated the biological and physical forcing within an upwelling patch by marking it with a tracer and sampling it for 9 days. They didn't include measurements of the surface microlayer (SML) and did not use a fresh upwelling patch. Their starting $p\text{CO}_2$ was around 540 μatm , where a $p\text{CO}_2$ of greater than 700 μatm can be found in this area.

Here we want to unravel the different processes (ASE, PP, mixing) in an fresh upwelling patch and observe the productivity directly. But especially for measuring ASE surface films have to be

taken into account for regions with high productivity. A recent analysis of satellite synthetic aperture radar (SAR) images from the region off West Africa showed that surface films develop rapidly after the onset of primary production (Alpers et al. 2013)). The authors could identify the reduction of sea surface roughness by the surfactants. Thus, it is crucial to measure the onset and development of the SML, while at the same time measuring high resolution gas fluxes and concentrations, in order to better estimate the importance of EBUS for global PP estimates and their impact on global trace gas budgets.

2.2 Literatur zu 2.1 (bitte eigene Arbeiten markieren)

- Alpers, W. et al., 2013. A small-scale oceanic eddy off the coast of West Africa studied by multi-sensor satellite and surface drifter data. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 129, pp.132–143.
- Arévalo-Martínez, D.L. et al., 2015. Massive nitrous oxide emissions from the tropical South Pacific Ocean. *Nature Geoscience*, 8(June), pp.530–533. Available at: <http://www.nature.com/doi/10.1038/ngeo2469>.
- Behrenfeld, M.J. et al., 2005. Carbon-based ocean productivity and phytoplankton physiology from space. *Global Biogeochem. Cycl.*, 19, p.GB1006.
- Businger, J.A., 1986. Evaluation of the Accuracy with which Dry Deposition Can be Measured with Current Micrometeorological Techniques. *Journal of Climate and Applied Meteorology*, 25, pp.1100–1124.
- Carr, M.-E. & Kearns, E.J., 2003. Production regimes in four Eastern Boundary Current systems. *Deep-Sea Res. II*, 50, pp.3199–3221.
- Chavez, F.P. & Toggweiler, J.R., 1995. Physical estimates of global new production: the upwelling contribution. In C. P. Summerhayes et al., eds. *Upwelling in the Ocean: Modern Processes and Ancient Records*. Wiley, Chichester, UK, pp. 313–320.
- Dugdale, R.C. & Goering, J.J., 1967. Uptake of New and Regenerated Forms of Nitrogen in Primary Productivity. *Limnol. Oceanogr.*, 12(2), pp.196–206.
- Forster, P. et al., 2007. Changes in Atmospheric Constituents and in Radiative Forcing. In S. Solomon et al., eds. *Climate Change 2007: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA: Cambridge University Press, pp. 129–234.
- Ho, D.T. et al., 2006. Measurements of air-sea gas exchange at high wind speeds in the Southern Ocean: Implications for global parameterizations. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 33(16), p.L16611.
- Jähne, B. & Haußecker, H., 1998. Air-water gas exchange. *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.*, 30, pp.443–468.
- Jähne, B., Heinz, G. & Dietrich, W., 1987. Measurement of the diffusion coefficients of sparingly soluble gases in water. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 92(C10), p.10767. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1029/JC092iC10p10767> [Accessed February 20, 2017].
- Kock, A. et al., 2012. Sea-to-air and diapycnal nitrous oxide fluxes in the eastern tropical North Atlantic Ocean. *Biogeosciences*, 9(3), pp.957–964.
- Koeve, W., 2004. Spring bloom carbon to nitrogen ratio of net community production in the temperate N. Atlantic. *Deep-Sea Res. I*, 51(11), pp.1579–1600.
- Körtzinger, A. et al., 2001. C : N ratios in the mixed layer during the productive season in the northeast Atlantic Ocean. *Deep-Sea Res. I*, 48.
- Lachkar, Z. & Gruber, N., 2012. Response of biological production and air–sea CO₂ fluxes to upwelling intensification in the California and Canary Current Systems. *Journal of Marine Systems*, 109–110, pp.149–160.
- Lachkar, Z. & Gruber, N., 2011. What controls biological production in coastal upwelling systems? Insights from a comparative modeling study. *Biogeosciences*, 8(10), pp.2961–2976.
- Loucaides, S. et al., 2012. Biological and physical forcing of carbonate chemistry in an upwelling filament off northwest Africa: Results from a Lagrangian study. *Global*

- Biogeochemical Cycles*, 26(3), pp.1–13.
- Messié, M. et al., 2009. Potential new production estimates in four eastern boundary upwelling ecosystems. *Progr. Oceanogr.*, 83, pp.151–158.
- Minas, H.J., Minas, M. & Packard, T.T., 1986. Productivity in upwelling areas deduced from hydrographic and chemical fields. *Limnol. Oceanogr.*, 31(6), pp.1182–1206.
- Mittelstaedt, E., 1983. The upwelling area off Northwest Africa—A description of phenomena related to coastal upwelling. *Progress in Oceanography*, 12(3), pp.307–331. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0079661183900125> [Accessed February 19, 2017].
- Pauly, D. & Christensen, V., 1995. Primary production required to sustain global fisheries. *Nature*, 374, pp.255–257.
- Sambrotto, R.N. et al., 1993. Elevated consumption of carbon relative to nitrogen in the surface ocean. *Nature*, 363, pp.248–250.
- Schmidt, R. & Schneider, B., 2011. The effect of surface films on the air–sea gas exchange in the Baltic Sea. *Mar. Chem.*, 126(1–4), pp.56–62.
- Steinhoff, T. et al., 2012. Biological productivity in the Mauritanian upwelling estimated with a triple gas approach. *Biogeoscience Discussion*, 9, pp.4853–4875.
- Thomas, H. et al., 1999. Preferential recycling of nutrients — the ocean’s way to increase new production and to pass nutrient limitation? *Limnol. Oceanogr.*, 44(8), pp.1999–2004.
- Tsai, W. & Liu, K., 2003. An assessment of the effect of sea surface surfactant on global atmosphere-ocean CO₂ flux. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 108(C4), pp.1–16.
- Wanninkhof, R. et al., 2009. Advances in Quantifying Air-Sea Gas Exchange and Environmental Forcing. *Ann. Rev. Mar. Sci.*, 1, pp.213–244.
- Wooster, W.S., Bakun, A. & McLain, D.R., 1976. The seasonal upwelling cycle along the eastern boundary of the North Atlantic. *J. Mar. Res.*, 34(2), pp.131–141.
- Wurl, O. et al., 2016. Biofilm-like properties of the sea surface and predicted effects on air-sea CO₂ exchange. *Progress in Oceanography*, 144, pp.15–24. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2016.03.002>.

2.3 Nationale und Internationale Einbindung

The objective of the cruise ties into the following international and national projects: Surface Ocean Lower Atmosphere Study (SOLAS), SOLAS mid-term research strategy for “air-sea gas fluxes in EBUS and OMZ systems” and the SFB 754. The underway data of this cruise will fill gaps in international databases for CO₂, N₂O, DMS and OCS (SOCAT, MEMENTO, PMEL-DMS seawater database). The participants of the cruise (please see section 5) are from various departments from GEOMAR. No money will be provided by the projects listed above.

3. Ziele und Arbeitsprogramm

3.1 Ziele

Here we propose a 3 week research cruise onboard R/V Poseidon to the Mauritanian upwelling region. The region off Mauritania offers an ideal study area for the proposed work: During the upwelling season (February – May) the contrast between high biological production near the coast and oligotrophic waters ca. 200 km offshore can be sampled within short timescales.

This natural setting allows us to work on the following main topics:

- *What is the impact of the different processes leading to the contrasting patterns of high supersaturation and values around equilibrium for various gases?*

Figure 3 shows a schematic of the different processes in a EBUS. Once the nutrient rich subsurface water reached the surface biological production starts. Furthermore freshly upwelled water is highly supersaturated in greenhouse gases (as CO₂, N₂O). The surface water concentration of these gases is decreasing with time (cf. Figure 1) due to the following processes: biological uptake, ASE and mixing. In order to estimate the productive strength and the impact on global budgets of these gases we want to unravel the different processes. We will identify a freshly upwelled water parcel and mark it with a surface drifter (Figure 4) which follows

the water in a quasi-Lagrangian way. This enables us to follow this water parcel for several days and study its dynamics. We will measure gas concentrations in the surface water and the overlying atmosphere and in addition we will measure directly the flux of CO₂ using the eddy-covariance method. We aim to follow the water parcel until all concentrations have reached equilibrium with the atmosphere or reach oligotrophic conditions. To estimate small scale mixing processes (as diapycnal mixing) regular measurements with the microstructure sonde will be conducted. Of high importance is the high frequent (up to twice a day) sampling of the SML as it plays an important role in ASE. For gases the SML can have a dampening effect on ASE, but there are also other emerging questions in the context of the SML: Which organisms (e.g. phytoplankton groups) are associated with the excretion of dissolved organic matter in the surface ocean? Which bacterial and phytoplankton taxa are associated with TEP in the surface and at depth?

For the first time we will be able to simultaneously (1) measure the concentration changes in the surface water of different gases, (2) measure their direct flux between the ocean and the atmosphere and (3) measure the development of the surface microlayer and its impact on ASE.

Figure 3: Overview over the processes that drive concentrations of various gases in upwelling region and that will be investigated during the proposed cruise.

- *What is the global impact of highly productive water masses on trace gas budgets? Is the upwelling area a net sink or source for trace gases, i.e. is there a carbon transport by particle in the deeper ocean that sequesters carbon?*

By unraveling the processes mentioned above we will be able to quantify the amount of carbon that is released to the atmosphere or sequestered in the ocean. By simultaneously measuring the concentration gradient of CO₂ between the ocean and the atmosphere and its direct flux we will be able to define different transfer coefficients for different phases of the observed water parcel, depending on the composition of the SML. In addition we will conduct CTD surveys around the drifter and along a section from open ocean waters onto the coast in order to resolve also the vertical distribution of the parameters of interest. These include measurements of particulate organic matter (POM) and other substances that are produced or consumed in highly productive waters (e.g. dimethylsulfide (DMS), carbonylsulfide (OCS)). Upwelling areas are hot-spots of the photochemically produced gases OCS and CS₂ (Lennartz et al., 2017, Atmos. Chem. Phys.). As these gases are photochemically produced their measurements are a good contrast to e.g. CO₂. With their measurements another aspect of gas production/consumption will be added to the underway measurements. Furthermore the data base for OCS and CS₂ is

very sparse on global scale and the measurements in the upwelling area off Mauritania will add more insight in their cycling. Both are of climate relevance as greenhouse gases and major supplier of stratospheric sulfur aerosol layer with implications for the earth's radiative budget.

3.2 Arbeitsprogramm

The cruise will start with a transit from Las Palmas/Spain to the working area off the coast of Mauritania. Once the EEZ of Mauritania is reached the scientific program will start. First the underway instruments will be started measuring SST, SSS, $p\text{CO}_2$, N_2O , O_2 , CS_2 and OCS continuously in the surface water. The cruise track will closely follow the coast line until approximately 17°N . By following the proposed cruise track we will cross freshly upwelled water masses. Based on the measured SST, concentration of trace gases and in correspondence with colleagues on land (analyzing satellite maps of SST, chlorophyll and sea surface heights) we will define a promising upwelling patch. The drifter will be outfitted with various sensors measuring in the mixed layer and will be deployed in this patch. The ship will be positioned in a way that the bow is heading to the drifter and into the wind. The drifter sends its position every 30 minutes. This will be displayed on a computer on the bridge which helps to stay in the vicinity of the drifter (see Figure 7). We aim for a drifter deployment of 13 days, which was shown in other studies to be sufficient to follow a freshly upwelling patch from the coast to open ocean waters (Steinhoff et al. (2012), Loucaides et al. (2012)).

The daily program during the drift station is shown in Figure 7. It consists of regular sampling from the continuous surface water line, CTD stations and zodiac deployments (if weather conditions allowing). Every second day the ship will leave the drifter station and follow a section from the open ocean (approximately 18°W) onto the shore. During this section we will have three CTD stations in order to resolve the whole water column.

Underway measurements: We will install a submersible pump in the ship's moon pool that supplies a continuous water flow to several instruments. The same water line will be used to take discrete samples for parameters that cannot be measured continuously and for evaluation of the continuous measurements. In addition a thermosalinograph will be installed next to the pump, so SST and SSS directly at the sea water intake will be available. Surface water will be continuously analyzed for $p\text{CO}_2$, O_2 , CO , N_2O , OCS and CS_2 . OCS is produced photochemically from chromophoric dissolved organic matter (CDOM). Thus CDOM absorption measurements will be conducted during the underway sampling.

Eddy covariance measurements: Direct flux measurements of CO_2 will be used to understand the physical and chemical constraints on gas exchange. These measurements will give an independent estimation of k . These measurements are made at the frequency of turbulent motions in the atmosphere (10^{-4} to 1 Hz) and averaged over 10 - 60 minute intervals. These short intervals correspond to the variability in physical forcings of gas exchange (e.g. wind bursts, breaking waves). No other technique provides the same ability to directly derive the gas transfer coefficient on the time scales of its forcing parameters. In addition, no other technique can illustrate the flux disconnect between the SML and the bulk water beneath.

Sulfur containing substances: A gas chromatograph coupled to a flame photometric detector (GC-FPD) will be used to measure discrete and underway samples for DMS, DMSP, and DMSO. These measurements will be used to investigate 1) the depth distribution of the short-lived sulphur compounds DMSP and DMSO as precursors of DMS; 2) the possible influence of low oxygen concentrations on DMS production; 3) the gas transfer coefficient of DMS (in conjunction with eddy covariance measurements); 4) the accuracy/ precision of various DMS measurement methods.

Physical measurements: Physical measurements will consist of conductivity-temperature-depths (CTD) profiles including water sampling. Microstructure measurements will be conducted to determine the turbulent mixing in the upper 200 m. Data analysis will allow quantifying the dominant CO₂, O₂, N₂O and nutrient flux contributions between the mixed layer and the deep water below. Additionally, SAR data will be available from RADARSAT-2 (Canadian satellite) and from RISAT (Indian satellite) to quantify the correlation of SAR-derived and measured surfactants concentrations. Furthermore the shipboard ADCP will use to measure the deeper currents.

Vertical profiles: The CTD profile stations will also be used to sample the vertical distribution of various parameters; e.g. O₂, CO₂, N₂O and nutrients will be sampled down to below the oxygen minimum, which is the area where N₂O is produced. Also various biological parameters are sampled (e.g. dissolved organic matter (DOM) and particulate organic matter (POM)) which will be used to estimate the export of carbon out of the upwelling patch.

Ocean optics: Various parameters can be measured by optical sensors (nitrate, chlorophyll, CDOM). These sensors will be included in the underway measurements and some of them will be also attached to the drifter. In conjunction with discrete sampling for e.g. nitrate we will gain information of their response over a huge range of concentration.

Ocean Surface Microlayer: To accurately quantify and predict gas fluxes to the atmosphere, the potential role of surfactants in wave dampening at the air-sea microlayer need to be understood. Sampling of the microlayer will be conducted manually from a zodiac using the glass plate technique (Stolle, Nagel et al. (2009), Aq. Microbial Ecol.). Underlying seawater (ULW) will be sampled using a hand-held water sampler from 20 cm below surface. The following variables will be determined: 1) dissolved organic carbon (DOC); 2) total dissolved nitrogen (TDN); 3) molecular composition of combined amino acids and carbohydrates; 4) total lipids; 5) concentration and size distribution of proteinaceous and carbohydrate gel articles (i.e. coomassie stained particles (CSP) and transparent exopolymer particles (TEP)); 6) chromophoric dissolved organic matter (CDOM) and bacterial abundance.

Highly sensitive IC- and HPLC-techniques will be applied to analyze concentrations and compositions of amino acids (DAA) and carbohydrates (DCHO) in DOM. Aside neutral sugars and amino sugars, a novel protocol for carbohydrate analysis will allow for the detection of the acidic sugars gluconic acid, glucuronic acid and galacturonic acid. CDOM and fluorescent DOM (FDOM) will be estimated from spectral absorption and from spectral fluorescent measurements, respectively.

Profiling pump: In addition to the CTD discrete sampling we will deploy a profiling pump. This pump is equipped with a thermosalinograph and can be lowered down to approximately 200m depth. This pump will be deployed once a day after the CTD stations and all underway instruments will be connected to its water supply. This allows us to obtain fine resolution profiles of the important compounds (CO₂, N₂O, O₂, OCS). The actual time of the day of the deployments will be varied in order to resolve diurnal cycles.

Drifter Deployment: In order to follow a water parcel in a quasi-Lagrangian approach a surface drifter will be used to mark a water patch. The drifter will be equipped with a satellite tracker and autonomous instrumentation at ca. 10 m water depth for in situ measurements of salinity, temperature, $p\text{CO}_2$, O_2 , gas tension, chlorophyll and nitrate (Figure 4). Depending on their power consumption there might be additional optical sensors that can be connected to the drifters power supply. Deploying the drifter for several days at different conditions (reaching from high productive to oligotrophic waters) will precisely resolve diel cycles that are superimposed to measured underway CO_2 and O_2 .

The drifter is equipped with a satellite communication head that transmits its position in defined time intervals (normally 30 minute interval). During night time one can switch on a flash light which makes the navigation easier. After one week the drifter will be recovered and the data will be saved. After the instruments are cleaned (biofouling) and new batteries are provided it will be deployed for another week.

Figure 5: Drifter deployment during the Sonne cruise SO235 in the Indian Ocean (T.Steinhoff, unpublished data). Top panel: Drifter track during a 24 hour period. Lower panel: Temperature, oxygen, $p\text{CO}_2$ and chlorophyll as recorded from the sensors attached to the drifters sensor cage. The diurnal cycle is clearly visible in all parameters.

Figure 4: Drifter with sensor package and communication buoy.

3.2.1 Arbeitsgebiet mit Stations- und Profilkarten

The cruise track is shown in Figure 2. From the start port there will be 3 days of transit (calculated with 7 kn). Once the EEZ of Mauritania is reached the underway measurements will be started. The cruise track will follow the coast line in order to identify a upwelling parcel (characterized by low temperature and e.g. high $p\text{CO}_2$ levels). Based on the position of this upwelled filament, the drifter will be deployed in this filament and the station work starts. The ship is supposed to follow the drifter in a way that the bow is pointing in the wind and heading to the drifter. Every second day a section from open ocean waters (approximately 18°W) heading to the coast is planned. During this section also shallow CTD stations are planned. The drifter will stay in the water as long as possible. After recovery the cruise track will go directly to the end port.

Figure 6: Planned cruise track. After a 3 day transit the cruise track follows the coastline of Mauritania in order to find a fresh upwelling patch.

3.2.2 Arbeiten in Hoheitsgebieten anderer Nationen – Forschungsgenehmigungen

The proposed cruise track covers three different EEZs (Spain, Sahara and Mauritania). However, within the Spanish and Saharian EEZs no scientific work is planned. A considerable amount of work is planned within the Mauritanian EEZ. As soon the ships proposal is granted I will start the diplomatic forms.

3.2.3 Einsatz von Geräten

We will require the use of the onboard CTD/rosette. The CTDs will be deployed to maximum depths of ~800 m. We will bring a profiling pump which will be deployed to a depth of ~200 m. This pump comes with its own winch. No other large instruments/equipment will be needed.

3.2.4 Besondere Anforderungen

For the eddy covariance measurements, the instrumentation should be as close to the bow as possible and a portable boom/mast outfitted with gas inlets, sampling tubing, electronic cables, and meteorological equipment is required as far forward as possible (to prevent turbulent flow distortion from the ship infrastructure). For the sampling of the microlayer we need regular zodiac deployments.

3.2.5 Arbeitstage

Table 1 outlines the approximate location of the first stations. The drift actual position of the drift station depends on the findings of the transect along the coast. The transit time until the EEZ of Mauritania is calculated to be 3 days using an average ships speed of 7kn. The drift experiment will be stopped in consultation with the ship's crew in order to allow for enough time to reach the end port. Here we calculated again 3 days for transit back to Las Palmas. We aim for at least 14 working days in the working area, which are divided in 2 days for finding an appropriate upwelling patch and 13 days of drifter deployment.

Table 1: Stationlist.

Way-point	Day of the cruise	Latitude	Longitude	Station	Distance to next WP (nm)	
1	1	28° 9' N	15° 25' W	Las Palmas(sp)	510	3 days transit
2	4	20° 0' N	17° 18' W	start underway program	255	1.5 days underway program along the coast to approximately 17°N, looking for a fresh upwelling patch
3	5	18° 1' N	16° 14' W	Drifter	133	Drifter deployment, 12 days station time
4	18	20° 0' N	17° 18' W	stop underway program	510	3 day transit
5	22	28° 9' N	15° 25' W	Las Palmas(sp)		

Figure 7: Schematic representation of the planned drift station. The ship should be positioned in a way that it is approximately located downwind of the drifter within 1 nm. Also shown is the planned sampling schedule for a typical day at the drift station. Details are given in section 3.2.

3.2.6 An- und Abreise

The proposed cruise will commence in Las Palmas, Spain and will end in Las Palmas, Spain. The first station is planned approximately 72 hours after departure and the last station will be sampled 72 prior to arrival in Las Palmas. The long transit on the way to the working area will also ensure that all instruments are working properly when following the upwelling patch. However, Mindelo/Cape Verde would be a good alternative as starting/ending port.

3.2.7 Maßnahmen zur verantwortungsvollen Meeresforschung

Water samples will be collected using either an underway pump system or a rosette configuration of niskin bottles attached to a conductivity, temperature and depth (CTD) profiler. The impact to the marine environment will therefore be negligible. There will be no investigation of benthic or zoological samples. No explosive or noise intensive measurements will be conducted. All chemicals used onboard will be brought back to the home labs.

4. Mittel für die Durchführung der Fahrt

N/A

5. Fahrtteilnehmer

I apply for 11 scientists berth including one observer from Mauritania. A detailed record is given in Table 4.

Table 4. Cruise participant information.

No.	Name	Working group/Duty	Affiliation	Status
1	Tobias Steinhoff	Underway CO ₂ , EC-CO ₂ , Drifter, CO ₂	GEOMAR	Chief scientist
2		EC-CO ₂ , DMS, Isoprene		
3		EC-CO ₂		
4		Underway N ₂ O		
5		Underway OCS		
6		Ocean optics		
7		Microlayer		
8		Microstructure, CTD		
9		Microlayer, Oxygen, nutrients		
10		Microstructure, CTD, Oxygen		
11		Observer Mauritania		

6. Daten-/Probensicherung und -verfügbarkeit

The Kiel Data Management Team (KDMT) maintains the Ocean Science Information System (OSIS) as a central information and research data sharing utility for marine research projects at GEOMAR and Kiel University. It is publicly accessible and can be utilized by all cruise participants, including national and international collaborators. OSIS merges information on expeditions, experiments and numerical models with peer review publications and available research data. The view of all information in OSIS is open to the public while access to actual data in ongoing research projects may be restricted for definable periods of time (moratorium). Alternatively the submission status of data files including the responsible investigator as contact person is visible to the public and may foster collaborations with interested researchers.

Members of the KDMT are active PANGAEA data curators and can assist researchers during preparation of their sample archival and data publication procedures in a World Data Center (e.g. PANGAEA) which will then warrant long-term archival and access to the research data. This data publication process will be based on available files in OSIS and is therefore transparent to all reviewers and other researchers.

Cooperation with a world data center and the union for application of International Geo Sample Numbers (IGSN) will make data and samples globally trackable and increase their scientific value and usability. Links to data publishers or principle investigators provide contact information for external scientists.

The chief scientist and all principal investigators involved in this cruise will comply with the time schedule below regulating the availability of all information and all research data and where applicable also of physical samples resulting from this cruise.

Following the cruise the KDMT will support and assist researchers in their data management activities.

Availability of metadata in OSIS (<https://portal.geomar.de/osis>): 2 weeks after completion of the cruise and related experiments
Availability of data in OSIS (<https://portal.geomar.de/osis>): 6 months after completion of the cruise and related experiments.
Availability of data in a WDC/PANGAEA (<http://www.pangaea.de> or as compilation at <http://www.pangaea.de/search?q=campaign:CRUISENAME>): 3 years after completion of the cruise and related experiments.

7. Erklärungen

„Die Unterzeichner verpflichten sich, die geplanten Forschungsaktivitäten im Rahmen der „Erklärung zu einer verantwortungsvollen Meeresforschung“ (Anlage 1 und 2) durchzuführen.“

8. Unterschrift(en)

Kiel, 20.02.2017

Dr. Tobias Steinhoff

9. Verzeichnis der Anlagen

1. Declaration of responsible marine research
3. OSPAR Code
3. CV of proponent

Anlage 1 - Erklärung zu einer verantwortungsvollen Meeresforschung

Vorbemerkungen

Als Meeresforscher schätzen und achten wir die Einzigartigkeit und Komplexität der Meeresumwelt. Daher haben wir ein besonderes Interesse am Erhalt dieses ökologisch, wissenschaftlich, kulturell und auch wirtschaftlich wertvollen Lebensraumes. Gerade durch die fundierten Kenntnisse sowie die Verwendung von spezialisiertem Gerät in der Meeresforschung, wie Forschungsschiffe und bemannte oder unbemannte Forschungstauchboote, sind Wissenschaftler die einzige Gruppe, die diese besondere Meeresumwelt beobachten und bewerten kann. Die Folgen wissenschaftlicher Arbeiten sind im Vergleich mit natürlichen Variationen (vulkanische/ tektonische Ereignisse, Rutschungen, Klimavariationen, etc.) oder Störungen durch andere menschliche Aktivitäten (z. B. Bergbau, Fischerei, Schifffahrt) generell als gering für die Untersuchungsgebiete einzuschätzen. Nichtsdestotrotz besteht die Möglichkeit, dass gewisse Forschungsaktivitäten einen – wenn auch ungewollten – negativen Nebeneffekt auf einzelne Gebiete oder Lebewesen haben.

Ein grundlegendes Verständnis des äußerst komplexen Meeressystems ist die beste Voraussetzung für den Schutz der Meere und dessen ökologisch tragfähige Nutzung. Dieses Verständnis ist jedoch nur durch wissenschaftliche Meeresforschung zu gewinnen. Daher muss die Meeresforschung integraler Bestandteil und Grundvoraussetzung für ein effektives Ressourcenmanagement und den Erhalt der natürlichen Biodiversität in den Meeren sein. Forschungsvorhaben müssen sich bemühen, einen möglichst natur- und umweltfreundlichen Ansatz zu wählen. Für die Bewilligung von Forschungsanträgen und Expeditionen sind die folgenden Grundsätze anzuwenden:

Grundsätze der verantwortungsvollen Meeresforschung

Als Mitglieder der internationalen Meeresforschungsgemeinschaft und im Sinne einer verantwortungsvollen Forschung fordern wir alle an Forschungsvorhaben beteiligten Wissenschaftler auf, die folgenden generellen Grundsätze bei Untersuchungen der Meere zu beachten:

- 1) Vermeidung von Aktivitäten im Rahmen von Forschungsvorhaben, die regionale Populationen oder prozentual hohe Individuenzahlen von Meeresorganismen nachhaltig beeinträchtigen könnten.
- 2) Vermeidung von Aktivitäten im Rahmen von Forschungsvorhaben, die wesentliche Veränderungen bzw. Schäden der marinen Ökosysteme (im physikalischen, chemischen, biologischen und geologischen Sinne) hervorrufen.
- 3) Bei Durchführung der Forschungsaktivitäten in ökologisch besonders sensiblen Gebieten (für den Nordatlantik und die Ostsee zum Beispiel die Habitats der OSPAR und HELCOM „List of threatened and/or declining species or habitats“; für andere Regionen gilt Entsprechendes) sowie in nationalen oder internationalen Meeresschutzgebieten ist Vorsorge zu treffen, dass Schutzgüter im Sinne der Schutzziele (insbesondere geschützte Arten und Biotope) gar nicht oder in möglichst geringem Umfang gestört oder geschädigt werden.

- 4) Vermeidung von Probenahmen, die im Rahmen des Forschungsvorhabens nicht notwendig sind.
- 5) Verwendung der jeweils am besten geeigneten und natur- und umweltschonenden Methodik für die Untersuchungen, soweit diese im zumutbaren Rahmen zur Verfügung stehen.
- 6) Sicherstellung, dass im Rahmen von Forschungsvorhaben die Umsetzung von Organismen zwischen verschiedenen Meeresgebieten, die potenziell den Lebensraum oder die Zusammensetzung der Lebensgemeinschaft permanent verändert, vermieden wird.
- 7) Vermeidung von Aktivitäten, die Experimente und Beobachtungen anderer Wissenschaftler beeinflussen würden. Dies erfordert, dass sich die Wissenschaftler mit gegenwärtigen und geplanten Forschungsvorhaben in dem betreffenden Meeresgebiet vertraut machen. Gleichzeitig sollte sichergestellt werden, dass eigene Forschungsvorhaben oder Pläne der internationalen Forschungsgemeinschaft mittels frei zugänglicher Datenbanken bekannt gemacht werden.
- 8) Sicherstellung einer möglichst breiten Verwendung von biologischen, chemischen und geologischen Proben, die im Rahmen von Kooperationen zwischen Wissenschaftsgemeinschaften gewonnen wurden. Archivierungsfähiges Probenmaterial sollte zur weiteren Nutzung für die wissenschaftliche Gemeinschaft verfügbar gehalten werden.
- 9) Bekenntnis zu einer internationalen Nutzung von Daten, Proben und Ergebnissen über entsprechende Datenbanken, um eine unnötige erneute Probenahme und Belastungen zu vermeiden und um ein globales Verständnis des marinen Lebensraumes zu fördern.

Die deutsche Meeresforschung unterstützt geeignete Forschungsprojekte, die die Erfassung, Erforschung, Bewertung und möglicherweise ökologische Optimierung der Effekte von Forschungstätigkeiten auf die Meeresnatur und -umwelt zum Ziel haben.

Die Senatskommission für Ozeanographie der Deutschen Forschungsgemeinschaft und das Konsortium Deutsche Meeresforschung (KDM) unterstützen uneingeschränkt, auch in Verantwortung gegenüber zukünftigen Generationen, die einzelnen Aussagen dieser Erklärung zu einer verantwortungsvollen wissenschaftlichen Meeresforschung und fordern alle Wissenschaftler auf, sich bei der Planung und Durchführung von Forschungsvorhaben den zuvor genannten Grundsätzen zu unterwerfen. Für die Bewilligung von Forschungsanträgen und Expeditionen ist die Anwendung dieser Grundsätze eine notwendige Voraussetzung.

OSPAR Code of Conduct for Responsible Marine Research in the Deep Seas and High Seas of the OSPAR Maritime Area

Version: 7-Mar-2008

Background

1. This code of conduct is based on the InterRidge Statement of Commitment to Responsible Research Practices at Deep-Sea Hydrothermal Vents, and an unofficial translation of the German Senatskommission für Ozeanographie / German Marine Consortium KDM, Commitment to Responsible Marine Research. It has been developed within the work programme of the OSDPAR Biodiversity Committee by an intersessional correspondence group on marine protected areas working in consultation with a number of deep sea scientists and experts. It is currently being circulated to European scientific bodies for further comment.
2. The OSPAR Maritime Area includes large areas of deep and high sea.² These are recognised as containing ecosystems that may have a lower resilience than shallower nearshore areas, including several species and habitats that can be vulnerable to human disturbances.
3. The OSPAR Commission has adopted, and keeps under review, an Initial OSPAR List of Threatened and/or Declining Species and Habitats (OSPAR agreement 2004/6) to guide the setting priorities for its further work on the conservation and protection of marine biodiversity. The species and habitats on this list, especially those occurring in high / deep sea areas, are vulnerable to different actual or potential human activities, including marine scientific research.
4. OSPAR acknowledges the provisions and entitlements of United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) and highlights that the General Principles for the Conduct of Marine Scientific Research set out therein require, *inter alia*, that marine scientific research shall be conducted in compliance with all relevant regulations adopted in conformity with UNCLOS including those for the protection and preservation of the marine environment.
5. OSPAR recognises that marine research scientists appreciate the uniqueness and complexity of the marine environment, and are therefore particularly interested in preserving this scientifically, aesthetically, ecologically, and potentially economically valuable environment. Because of the specialized nature of the equipment required to work in the deep-sea, such as manned and unmanned research submersibles, scientists are the primary group of people who have had the opportunity to visit and value these extraordinary habitats. OSPAR also recognises that scientists have already worked to develop codes of conduct for some deep-sea features, such as hydrothermal vents and cold water corals, and this OSPAR code of conduct has been written to fit harmoniously with those. (Specific provisions concerning the conduct of scientific research in certain deep / high seas habitats will be attached as annexes to this statement as they are developed.)
6. The potential impact of many scientific activities on the marine environment is low in comparison to the potential for disturbance by natural processes (e.g. volcanic/tectonic events, slumps, climate variation, etc.) or other human activities (e.g. mining, fisheries, and shipping). Indeed many areas, especially seamounts and cold coral reefs, have been widely impacted by human activities, like fisheries, long before being scientifically studied. Nonetheless, there remains the possibility that some scientific activities could have unwanted negative side-effects on particular regions or animals if research activities are not carefully planned and executed. In addition, because only a limited number of sites are currently known and scientists from a wide variety of disciplines frequently work at these single locations, there is

² For the purposes of this document, *deep sea* shall follow the FAO definition and mean areas of the sea deeper than 200 metres, and *high seas* shall mean the water column and / or the seabed in areas beyond national jurisdiction, within the OSPAR Maritime Area.

the potential for conflicting effects among studies, and multiple impacts, particularly at sites where scientific activity is intense.

7. OSPAR recognises that protection and sustainable use of the oceans is best served by a fundamental understanding of its complex marine ecosystems, and that can only be achieved through marine research. OSPAR further recognises that the role of scientists is also of primary importance concerning the implementation of the OSPAR network of Marine Protected Areas, and this should be preceded with the best available science.

8. Thus, marine research is a prerequisite and an integral component of an ecosystem based management of marine resources and the effective conservation of biodiversity of the deep and high seas. Most forms of observation and investigation of natural systems involve some disturbance of the systems being studied. In the interest of environmental stewardship, it must be the goal of research scientists to minimize disturbances as much as possible, while still gathering the information necessary both to understand the systems and to form a basis for sustainable use strategies. Therefore, marine scientists should always evaluate their research plans from a conservative standpoint, and choose the most environmentally friendly research approach.

9. When awarding research grants or research cruise time, the research plans should be assessed against conformity with the following principles.

Conduct of responsible marine science

10. OSPAR requests all scientists working in the deep seas and high seas of the OSPAR maritime area to adhere to the following principles when conducting their work:

- a. **Species:** avoid, in the course of scientific research, activities which could lead to long-lasting changes in regional populations or substantially reduce the number of individuals present.
- b. **Habitats:** avoid, in the course of scientific research, activities which could lead to substantial physical, chemical, biological or geological changes or damage to marine habitats.
- c. **Threatened and/or declining features:** When working in areas of particular ecological vulnerability, including, *inter alia*, the features listed in the OSPAR “List of Threatened and/or Declining Species and Habitats” utmost care should be taken not to disturb or damage the features as far as possible.
- d. **Management areas / marine protected areas:** When working in areas of particular ecological importance and/or sensitivity, including, *inter alia*, OSPAR marine protected areas, care has to be taken not to disturb or damage the protected features, and that activities are in compliance with regulations for the area. Further, scientists are requested to respect the importance of management areas like marine protected areas and are asked to assist in their implementation through the use of the best scientific knowledge.
- e. **Notification and research planning:** Avoid activities which could disturb the experiments and observations of other scientists. This requires that scientists: a) make themselves familiar with the status of current and planned research in an area; and b) that they ensure that their own research activities and plans are known to the rest of the international research community via appropriate public domain data bases and web sites.
- f. **Methods:** Use the most environmentally-friendly and appropriate study methods which are reasonably available.
- g. **Transport of biota:** Ensure that transport of biota between different marine regions, which could lead to changes in the environment or the composition of marine communities, does not occur.
- h. **Collections:** Avoid collections that are not essential to the conduct of the scientific research, and reduce the number of samples to the necessary minimum.

- i. **Collaboration and cooperation:** Ensure the fullest possible use of all biological, chemical and geological samples through collaborations and cooperation within the global community of scientists. Samples which can be archived should be placed in accessible repositories for future use.
 - j. **Data-sharing:** Practise international sharing of data, samples and results in order to minimize the amount of unnecessary sampling and to further a global understanding of the marine environment.
11. OSPAR supports the individual points of this commitment unreservedly and requests all scientists to adhere to them when planning and carrying out their research.
12. Their application should be a prerequisite for the granting of research funds and ship time.

ANLAGE 3
Curriculum Vitae

Dr. Tobias Steinhoff

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Born 09. August 1973 in Wolfsburg/Germany
German

Education and professional experience

01/11-present	Postdoc, GEOMAR, Kiel
12/10	Ph.D. in Marine Chemistry (University of Kiel)
03/05-12/10	Ph.D. student, Leibniz Institute for Marine Sciences, Kiel
04/00-12/04	Study of Chemistry (University of Kiel)
10/95 – 03/00	Study of Mathematics/Chemistry pursuing teaching certification (University of Kiel)

Cruises (since 2012: Leadership role highlighted)

10/15	R/V Sonne (SO243) – southern Pacific Ocean, co-chief scientist, co-proponent
08/14	R/V SONNE (SO235) – Indian Ocean, Scientist, involved in logistics and cruise planning
07/14	R/V SONNE (SO234-1) – Indian Ocean, Scientist, involved in logistics and cruise planning
07/13	<i>R/V Meteor (M98)</i> – southern Atlantic Ocean, Scientist
10/12	<i>R/V Maria S. Merian (MSM22)</i> – tropical Atlantic Ocean, Scientist

Since 2006 I am responsible for continuous underway measurements of $p\text{CO}_2$ and O_2 onboard a container ship crossing the North Atlantic between UK and Canada. During this time I organized a huge sampling program onboard this vessel by sending students with the vessel or joining the ship by myself.

Publications (since 2008):

Arévalo-Martínez, D.L., M. Beyer, M. Krumbholz, I. Piller, A. Kock, **T. Steinhoff**, A. Körtzinger, and H. W. Bange (2013). A new method for continuous measurements of oceanic and atmospheric N_2O , CO and CO_2 : performance of off-axis integrated cavity output spectroscopy (OA-ICOS) coupled to non-dispersive infrared detection (NDIR). *Ocean Sci. Discuss.*, 10, 1281 – 1327.

Arevalo-Martinez, D. L., Kock, A., **Steinhoff, T.**, Brandt, P., Dengler, M., Fischer, T., Körtzinger, A. und Bange, H. W. Nitrous oxide during the onset of the Atlantic Cold Tongue. *JGR - Oceans*. DOI 10.1002/2016JC012238.

Fietzek, P., B. Fiedler, **T. Steinhoff**, and A. Körtzinger (2013). In situ quality assessment of a novel underwater $p\text{CO}_2$ sensor based on membrane equilibration and NDIR spectrometry. *J. Atmos. Oceanic Technol.* doi:10.1175/JTECH-D-13-00083.1, in press

Steinhoff, T., H.W. Bange, A. Kock, D.W.R. Wallace und A. Körtzinger (2012). Biological Productivity in the Mauritanian upwelling estimated with a triple gas approach. *Biogeosciences Discuss.*, 9, 4853-4875.

- Becker, M., N. Andersen, B. Fiedler, P. Fietzek, A. Körtzinger, **T. Steinhoff**, and G. Friedrichs (2012). Using cavity ringdown spectroscopy for continuous monitoring of $\delta^{13}\text{C}(\text{CO}_2)$ and $f\text{CO}_2$ in the surface ocean. *Limnol. Oceanogr.: Methods*, 10, 752-766.
- C. Le Quéré, ... **T. Steinhoff**,... (2015) Global Carbon Budget 2015. *Earth System Science Data*, 7, 349-396.
- Quay, P., J., Stutsman and **T. Steinhoff** (2012). Primary production and carbon export rates across the subpolar North Atlantic Ocean basin based on triple oxygen isotope and dissolved O_2 and Ar gas measurements. *Global Biogeochem. Cycles*, 26 (2), doi: 10.1029/2010GB004003.
- Steinhoff, T.**, T. Friedrich, S.E. Hartman, A. Oschlies, D.W.R. Wallace und A. Körtzinger (2010). Estimating mixed layer nitrate in the North Atlantic Ocean. *Biogeosciences*, 7, 795-807.
- Watson, A.J., U. Schuster, D.C.E. Bakker, N.R. Bates, A. Corbière, M. González-Dávila, T. Friedrich, J. Hauck, C. Heinze, T. Johannessen, A. Körtzinger, N. Metzl, J. Olafsson, A. Olsen, A. Oschlies, X. A. Padin, B. Pfeil, J.M. Santana-Casiano, **T. Steinhoff**, M. Telszewski, A.F. Rios, D.W.R. Wallace, R. Wanninkhof (2009). Tracking the Variable North Atlantic Sink for Atmospheric CO_2 . *Science*, 326 (5958), doi:10.1126/science.1177394.
- Takahashi, T, S.C. Sutherland, R. Wanninkhof, C. Sweeney, R.A. Feely, D.W. Chipman, B. Hales, G. Friederich, F. Chavez, C. Sabine, A. Watson, D.C.E. Bakker, U. Schuster, N. Metzl, H. Yoshikawa-Inoue, M. Ishii, T. Midorikawa, Y. Nojiri, A. Körtzinger, **T. Steinhoff**, M. Hoppema, J. Olafsson, T.S. Arnarson, B. Tilbrook, T. Johannessen, A. Olsen, R. Bellerby, C.S. Wong, B. Delille, N.R. Bates und H.J.W. de Baar (2009). Climatological mean and decadal change in surface ocean pCO_2 , and net sea-air CO_2 flux over the global oceans. *Deep-Sea Res. II*, 56, 554-577.